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SCIENTIFIC SUBSTANTIATION OF THE CONCEPTUAL APPROACHES TO THE DEVELOPMENT OF NEW PROGRAMMES FOR DRINKING WATER QUALITY MONITORING

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НАУЧНОЕ ОБОСНОВАНИЕ КОНЦЕПТУАЛЬНЫХ ПОДХОДОВ К РАЗРАБОТКЕ НОВЫХ ПРОГРАММ МОНИТОРИГА КАЧЕСТВА ПИТЬЕВЫХ ВОД

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НАУКОВЕ ОБГРУНТУВАННЯ КОНЦЕПТУАЛЬНИХ ПІДХОДІВ ДО РОЗРОБКИ НОВИХ ПРОГРАМ МОНІТОРИНГУ ЯКОСТІ ПИТНИХ ВОД

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Summary/Резюме

We substantiated scientifically and improved the algorithm of the hygienic assessment and monitoring of drinking water quality. We performed the analysis of the European and the Ukrainian normative documents on natural and drinking water quality. The results of the study of tap drinking water quality from surface and underground sources of drinking water supply, in the points of bottling and packed in different oblasts of Ukraine (over 600 samples) for the last 17 years were analyzed. In the study we used the following methods: bibliographic (analysis of scientific information), sanitary-and-hygienic, sanitary-and-chemical, and method of expert assessment. For the implementation of the European legislation we developed substantiated scientifically changes to the National Sanitary Rules and Norms 2.2.4-171-10 (NSRN 2.2.4-171-10) "Hygienic Requirements to Drinking Water Intended for Human Consumption", complementing the minimum requirements of the Directive 98/83 EU, which include the European procedure of drinking water quality monitoring in the points of compliance and proposals on the improvement of the procedure of drinking water quality control after purification directly, meaning of "indicator parameters" and their extended list concerning

indicated one in the Directive 98/83EU. We developed the algorithm of the research for the fulfillment of the Directive 98/83EU requirements (taking into account the changes of 2015) concerning radiation. The main criterion of the assessment were established, it should be taken into account when making decisions on drinking water safety by “indicator parameters”. After scientific substantiation, we initiated the introduction of the meaning of “points of drinking water quality” for the first time. The term determinations of “production of drinking water” and “drinking water” were changed. In connection with the changes in the Ukrainian legislation and the requirements of the Directive 98/83 EU it is necessary to introduce the changes in the NSRN 2.2.4-171-10 “Hygienic Requirements to Drinking Water Intended for Human Consumption” concerning the new procedure of drinking water quality monitoring.

Key words: *points of compliance, programmes of monitoring, indicator parameters.*

Цель — научно обосновать и усовершенствовать алгоритм гигиенической оценки и мониторинга качества питьевых вод.

Материалы и методы. Проведен анализ европейской и украинской нормативной документации относительно качества природных и питьевых вод, проанализированы результаты исследований питьевых вод водопроводных из поверхностных и подземных источников питьевого водоснабжения, в пунктах разлива и фасованных на протяжении последних 17 лет в разных областях Украины (более 600 проб). При проведении исследований использованы методы: библиографический (анализ научной информации), санитарно-гигиенические, санитарно-химические и экспертной оценки.

Результаты. С целью имплементации европейского законодательства разработаны научно обоснованные изменения к ГСанПиН 2.2.4-171-10 «Гигиенические требования к воде питьевой, предназначенной для потребления человеком», дополняющие минимальные требования Директивы 98/83/ЕС, которые включают европейский порядок проведения мониторинга качества питьевой воды в пунктах соответствия, а также предложения по усовершенствованию порядка контроля качества питьевой воды непосредственно после обработки, понятие «индикаторных показателей» и их расширенный перечень относительно указанного в Директиве 98/83/ЕС. Разработан алгоритм проведения исследований для выполнения требований Директивы 98/83/ЕС (с учетом изменений 2015 г.) относительно радиационного загрязнения и определены основные критерии оценки, которые должны приниматься во внимание при принятии решений относительно безопасности питьевой воды по «индикаторным показателям». По нашей инициативе в Закон Украины «Про питьевую воду и питьевое водоснабжение» после научного обоснования впервые было введено понятие «пункты соответствия качества питьевой воды», изменено определение термина «производство питьевой воды» и «питьевая вода».

Заключение. В связи с изменениями украинского законодательства и требований Директивы 98/83/ЕС необходимо внесение научно обоснованных изменений в ГСанПиН 2.2.4-171-10 «Гигиенические требования к воде питьевой, предназначенной для потребления человеком» относительно нового порядка мониторинга качества питьевых вод.

Ключевые слова: вода питьевая, пункты соответствия, программы мониторинга, индикаторные показатели, радионуклиды.

Мета — науково обґрунтувати та удосконалити алгоритм гігієнічної оцінки та моніторингу якості питних вод.

Матеріали та методи. Проведено аналіз європейської та української нормативної документації щодо якості природних та питних вод, проаналізовані результати досліджень питних вод водопровідних з поверхневих і підземних джерел питного водопостачання, в пунктах розливу і фасованих протягом останніх 17 років в різних областях України (понад 600 проб). При проведенні досліджень використані методи: бібліографічний (аналіз наукової інформації), санітарно-гігієнічні, санітарно-хімічні та експертної оцінки.

Результати. З метою імплементації європейського законодавства розроблено науково обґрунтовані зміни до ДСанПіН 2.2.4-171-10 «Гігієнічні вимоги до води питної, призначеної для споживання людиною», що доповнюють мінімальні вимоги Директиви 98/83/ЄС, які включають європейський порядок проведення моніторингу якості питної води в пунктах відповідності, а також пропозиції щодо вдосконалення порядку контролю якості питної води безпосередньо після обробки, поняття «індикаторних показників» і їх розширений перелік відносно зазначеного у Директиві 98/83/ЄС. Розроблено алгоритм проведення досліджень для виконання вимог Директиви 98/83/ЄС (з урахуванням змін 2015 р.) щодо радіаційного забруднення та визначено основні критерії оцінки, які повинні прийматися до уваги у разі прийняття рішень щодо безпеки питної води за «індикаторними показниками». За нашою ініціативою до Закону України «Про питну воду та питне водопостачання» після наукового обґрунтування вперше було введено поняття «пункти відповідності якості питної води», змінено визначення термінів «виробництво питної води» та «питна вода».

Висновок. У зв'язку із змінами українського законодавства та вимог Директиви 98/83/ЄС необхідно внесення науково обґрунтованих змін у ДСанПіН 2.2.4-171-10 «Гігієнічні вимоги до води питної, призначеної для споживання людиною» щодо нового порядку моніторингу якості питних вод.

Ключові слова: вода питна, пункти відповідності, програми моніторингу, індикаторні показники, радіонукліди.

Introduction

The work was performed within the project “Support of Ukraine in the Approximation of the European Legislation” (APENA Project) for the implementation of the Directive 98/83 EU “On Drinking Water Intended for Human Consumption” (with changes of 2015) in Ukraine and because of the changes introduced in 2017 in the Law

of Ukraine “On Drinking Water and Drinking Water Supply”. We had carried out a comparative analysis of the procedure of drinking water quality monitoring in Europe (Directive 98/83 EU) and production control in Ukraine (NSRN 2.2.4-171-10), then we improved the methodology of the appropriate monitoring for the introduction in Ukraine on the basis of many years study experience of natural and drinking water quality and impact of drinking water quality on the health of the consumers.

Objective

We substantiated scientifically and improved the algorithm of the hygienic assessment and monitoring of drinking water quality.

Materials and methods

We performed the analysis of the European and the Ukrainian normative documents on natural and drinking water quality. For the last 17 years we have been studying quality of tap drinking water from surface and underground sources of drinking water supply, in the places of bottling and packed in different oblasts of Ukraine (over 600 samples). In the study we used the following methods: bibliographic (analysis of scientific information), sanitary-and-hygienic, sanitary-and-chemical, and method of expert assessment.

Results and discussion

In 2015 a statement that “water is a food product” was introduced in the Law of Ukraine “On the Main Principles and Requirements to the Safety and Quality of Food Product”, it conflicted with the European Directive N178/2002, 28.01.02. For the implementation of the European legislation, we initiated [10] the changes in the Law of Ukraine “On Drinking Water and Drinking Water Supply”. According to these changes, a drinking water is not a food product in the system of drinking water supply and in the points of the compliance of drinking water quality. And there is an explanation: at the normalization of drinking water quality the principles are used which take into account the multiphase of its use, local nature conditions, etc. It is not taken into account at the normalization of safety and food products’ quality. Besides, drinking water must become one of the objects of combined ecological monitoring of natural and drinking

water.

Monitoring of drinking water quality should be carried out according to the Directive 98/83 EU (with the changes of 2015) in the points of compliance where a compliance of drinking water with the hygienic requirements is established, viz.:

- from the taps of drinking water supply system — for tap drinking water;
- in the places of bottling in the consumer’s containers — for packed drinking water;
- in the places of bottling in the consumer’s containers — for drinking water from the points of bottling;
- in the places of the use at the enterprises — for drinking water used for industrial (technological) needs.

Mentioned monitoring programmes for water intended for human consumption must:

- a) verify that the measures to control risks to the consumers’ health at all stages of drinking water supply from the catchment area through its treatment, storage, and distribution and that water at the points of compliance is wholesome and clean;
- b) provide information on the quality of drinking water and demonstrate its compliance with standard requirements;
- c) identify the most appropriate measures of mitigating the risk to negative impact of drinking water to the consumers’ health.

On the basis of mentioned above, the competent authorities should develop the programme for drinking water monitoring (technological instruction). At the development of this

program we propose to analyze: results of water monitoring of drinking water supply source, features of the technology of its treatment, conditions of storage and transportation, efficiency of drinking water supply systems, presence of problematic parameters of drinking water quality, etc.

According to the Directive 98/83/EU the programmes should consist of:

- a) collection and analysis of the quality of selected water samples; and/or
- b) measurements recorded by a continuous monitoring process.

Besides, the monitoring programmes may consist of:

- a) Inspections of records of the functionality and maintenance status of equipment; and/or
- b) Examination of the catchment areas and water abstraction, treatment, storage and distribution infrastructure.

Drinking water monitoring should be carried out constantly, examinations of selected samples should reflect its quality during a year. The monitoring programmes may be based on general principles of risk assessment presented in the international standards, such as the Standard EN 15975-2 and take into account the results of the programmes of water objects' monitoring (Directive 2000/60/EU). Mentioned assessment is carried out for the determination of the possibility to introduce changes into the procedure of water quality monitoring in the points of compliance. E.g., at the presence of water supply network the samples can be collected in a zone of water supply or at the treatment plants (after purification) for definite quality parameters if it is possible to prove that the content of the substance cannot be deteriorated during transportation of drinking water in the water supply network. For risk assessment, a number

of the parameters for the monitoring of drinking water quality or the frequency of sampling can be increased or decreased if risk assessment corroborates that any potentially possible factor may not lead to the deterioration of drinking water and consumer's health will be protected. The monitoring programmes (on the basis of risk assessment or without it) should be reviewed on a continuous basis and updated or reconfirmed every five years, and a short report of the results of risk assessment must be an available information.

The Directive 98/83/EU contains the minimum requirements to the procedure of monitoring, every three years by its results the EU countries publish a report on drinking water quality and measures which are planned or were performed for the fulfillment of the requirements of the Directive 98/83/EU to inform the consumers and other EU countries.

Comparative assessment of the Directive 98/83/EU and the NSRN 2.2.4-171-10 concerning the procedure of drinking water quality monitoring by microbiological and organoleptic parameters demonstrated that, at the efficiency of water supply of 130 000 m³/day, the more strict control was in the NSRN 2.2.4-171-10. Therefore, for the maximum decrease of risk of poor quality water supply, the procedure, shown in the Directive, should be extended, at least, in the points directly after water purification where drinking water quality must be controlled on the content of the organoleptic and microbiological parameters and also:

1. Residual concentrations of coagulants and flocculants, in case of their use (aluminium, common iron, polyphosphates, polyacrylamide, silicon, etc.) — not less than once a shift (complies with

- the requirements of the NSRN 2.2.4-171-10).
2. Residual concentrations of the disinfection reagents in case of their use — not less than once an hour (complies with the requirements of NSRN 2.2.4-171-10).
 3. Chlorine dioxide, residual free chlorine and chlorites in case of the chlorine dioxide treatment- not less than once an hour (it was demonstrated for the first time that it was necessary to control chlorine at water treatment with chlorine dioxide) [7].
 4. Chlorates, in case of chlorine dioxide treatment — not less than once a month [7] (it was regulated for the first time). According to WHO recommendations it is necessary to toughen the hygienic standards for chlorates (0.7 mg/l) and, therefore, a risk of their occurrence in an over-standard amount increases, as a necessity of their control in drinking water.
 5. Trihalomethanes (a sum), in case of the introduction of the methods for the minimization of the formation of trihalomethanes in chlorinated water from the surface source of drinking water supply (pre-ammonization, etc.) or additional purification of chlorinated tap drinking water from surface source of drinking water supply from trihalomethanes (sorption, etc.) — not less than once three months (it was regulated for the first time).
According to the results of our studies, trihalomethanes are one of the priority pollutants in the above types of drinking water and are detected in more than 50 % of the samples among the total number of non-standard samples. It's due to the insufficient control by the controlling authorities and their rare establishment at the production control (for points of bottling — once a year).
 6. Added macro- and microelements in case of artificial mineralization of drinking water (pre-mineralization, fluoration, iodation, etc.) at the points of bottling with the efficiency < 5 m³/daily, minimum once a week. The results of our studies revealed that to date, a large number of drinking water produced with a dry residue of less than 100 mg/l, which is prohibited NSRN 2.2.4-171-10. Among the total number of inadequate quality samples from underground sources — 24 % of samples, purified water from surface sources — 36 % of samples. The market demand and economic benefits are the reasons of such a situation. To change the situation created we propose to decrease a frequency of the control of the substances which are added into water, taking into account that the producers, as a rule, use the cartridge system of filtration and automated dosage systems.
 7. Parameters of drinking water quality which can be changed due to the performance of mentioned measures — after re-equipment of water supply system and changes in the technology of water preparation (the requirement of the NSRN 2.2.4-171-10 was changed). Today it is necessary to perform a total analysis that may be factually and economically inexpedient.
We revealed that the requirements of the existing NSRN 2.2.4-171-10 to the list of the parameters of drinking water quality were as close as possible to the requirements of the Directive 98/83/EU [12]. However, due to different reasons, 9 parameters were not

introduced into this document. These parameters must be in the national normative document at the implementation of the above Directive (Table 1).

According to the Directive 98/83/EU it is necessary to introduce a concept of “indicator parameters” in the National Sanitary Rules and Norms 2.2.4-171-10. About 20 parameters belong to them, among them are: 15 sanitary-and-chemical, 5 microbiological and radiological. Indicator parameters should be established both for the quantitative assessment and observation of the changes of drinking water quality (monitoring). In case of over-standard content of indicator (-s) parameter (-s), the executive body, realizing a state policy in the sphere of sanitary legislation, must solve whether an appropriate quality of drinking water presents a certain risk to the health of the consumers. If it is necessary, they must take actions for the improvement of drinking water quality.

In the Directive there is no algorithm for decision-making on the safety of drinking water in case of the over-standard content of the “indicator parameters”. In our opinion, at the making of the appropriate decisions, it is necessary to take into account the following criteria of the assessment: frequency and multiplicity of the excess by the parameter of the hygienic standard (it is necessary to take into account that the importance of the excess of the standard is estimated individually for each parameter), class of danger and its limiting feature of harmfulness, quantity of the parameters in the over -standard concentrations, reasons of their presence in water, absence of negative impact on the parameters of epidemic safety, background concentrations in the water

of the source, local conditions, factual morbidity of the consumers due to this reason (if it is proved by the epidemiological research), etc. The following hygienic standards should be accepted for: ammonium — 2.6 mg/l; aluminium — 0.5 mg/l; iron-1.0 mg/l; manganese — 0.5 mg/l; chlorides — 350 mg/l; sulphates -500 mg/l; dry residue — 1500 mg/l; colourity — 35 degrees; turbidity — 3.5 NTU (indicated in NSRN 2.2.4-171-10 as acting until 01.01.2020).

A number of the parameters in the national normative document may be increased in comparison with the list in the Directive 98/83/EU, and the standards may be more tough ones, at the presence of the scientific substantiation, where it is necessary for the protection of the morbidity of the population. Performed epidemiological research [5] verified a necessity of the standardization of dry residue in drinking water. It is absent in the Directive 98/83/EU. It was revealed that 1150 cases of blood circulation system diseases per 100 thousand people among the inhabitants of the city of Kherson were connected with increased mineral content of drinking water (a dry residue was at the level of 1777.7 ± 225.5 mg/l in 2004-2013). Obtained results of correlative and regressive analyses coincide practically with the international scientific research in the sphere of the impact of mineral components of drinking water on the population's morbidity [1, 4, 9, 8, 11].

According to the requirements of the Directive 98/83/EU, it is necessary to introduce changes in NSRN 2.2.4-171-10 in the part of the procedure of the monitoring of radiation water pollution. Water quality by the radiation parameters should be determined by the specific activity of tritium and radon (standard — 100 Bq/l) and a total

Table 1.

Parameters to be entered in the NSRM 2.2.4-171-10, current norms and factors of their presence in drinking water

Name of index	Factor of pollution presence in drinking water	Requirements	
		Directive 98/83 EU	in Ukraine (SRN 4630-88)
Bromates	Chlorination with electrolytic hypochlorite, ozonation or pollution of the initial water	0,025 µg/l	-
Multinuclear aromatic hydrocarbons (sum of concentrations: Benzo(b)fluoranthene, Benzo(k)fluoranthene, Benzo(ghi)perylene, Indeno(1,2,3-cd)pyrene)	Pollution of the initial water with the substances on the basis of oil	0,1 µg/l	-
Epichlorohydrin	Use of polyamine reagents, surfaces covered with some enamels	0,1 µg/l	10,0 µg/l
Vinyl chloride	Use of the appropriate polymer materials	0,5 µg/l	50,0 µg/l
Acrylamide	Use of the appropriate reagents	0,1 µg/l	10,0 µg/l
Indicator parameters			
Clostridium perfringens (including spores)	Long-standing faecal and remote water pollutions	0/100 ml	-
Electric conductivity	Natural or technogenic pollution of the initial water with salts, including salts of hardness	2500 µS cm ⁻¹ at 20 °C	-
Tritium and radon	Natural or technogenic radiation pollution of the initial water	100 Bq/l	-
Total indicative dose		0,1 mSv/year	-

indicative dose (0.1µSv/year) in the places of water intake. A total indicative dose is measured by the total activity of uranium, ²²⁶Ra, ²²⁸Ra, ²¹⁰Pb and ²¹⁰Po. In case of technogenic impact, depending on the situation, a contribution of ¹³⁷Cs, ⁹⁰Sr and other radionuclides is taken into account. A year volume of drinking water consumption and dose coefficients for radionuclides, applying for the calculation of total indicative dose, are presented in Table 2 [3].

Measurements of the specific activity of tritium, radon and total alpha- and beta-activity are admitted as a preliminary assessment of the radiation quality of water. If the parameters of total alpha- activity don't exceed a value of 0.1 Bq/l and the parameters of total beta-activity don't exceed a value of 1.0 Bq/l, then the total dose doesn't exceed a value of 0.1µSv/year. If it is established that the parameters of total alpha- activity and /or total beta-activity are exceeded, it is necessary to

determine the specific activities of separate radionuclides and to calculate the total indicative dose. In some cases it is necessary to repeat the measurement of prepared samples for decision-making about compliance with the requirements of the standards [2]. One should pay attention that the fulfillment of the requirements of the Directive 98/83/EU is the most complex for such categories of the population as children and newborns [6].

The above requirements to drinking water quality monitoring must be extended to all kinds of drinking water (tap, before bottling in consumer or individual containers of the consumers, after post purification of tap drinking water, from the pumphouses, wells and catchments of the sources) and are necessary for all who are engaged in the production of drinking water, i.e. water drain from the sources of drinking water supply and/or adjustment of its quality up to the requirements to drinking water (the

Table 2.

Dose coefficients of radionuclides in case of internal intake

Age group	Consumption of water for a year, l	Dose coefficients, Sv/Bq				
		²²⁶ Ra	²²⁸ Ra	Uranium	²¹⁰ Pb	²¹⁰ Po
Children < 1 year	250	4.70E-06	3.00E-05	3.40E-07	8.40E-06	2.60E-05
1 — 2 years	350	9.60E-07	5.70E-06	1.20E-07	3.60E-06	8.80E-06
2 — 7 years	350	6.20E-07	3.40E-06	8.00E-08	2.20E-06	4.40E-06
7 — 12 years	350	8.00E-07	3.90E-06	6.80E-08	1.90E-06	2.60E-06
12-17 years	540	1.50E-06	5.30E-06	6.70E-08	1.90E-06	1.60E-06
adults	730	2.80E-07	6.90E-07	4.50E-08	6.90E-07	1.20E-06

requirements of the NSRN 2.2.4-171-10 were changed). For this purpose, in 2017 we initiated a change of the term of “drinking water production” in the Law of Ukraine “On Drinking Water and Drinking Water Supply”. Today the monitoring of drinking water should be carried out for technological water at the enterprises of food industry except cases when the executive body, realizing a state policy in the field of sanitary legislation, considers that the use of such water doesn’t affect the safety of finished food product. The requirements of the national standard document may not be disseminated on the water of drinking water supply systems for the individual use from individual sources with the average efficiency less than 10 m³ daily or such ones that are used by less than 50 persons, if this drinking water isn’t used for commercial purpose or for public use. However, the consumers of such drinking water should be informed about this and about measures that may be taken for the protection of their health in case of drinking water pollution.

Conclusions

1. Algorithm of the new procedure of drinking water monitoring was scientifically substantiated and

improved. In terms of this algorithm, the European procedure of drinking water quality monitoring should be introduced in existing now NSRN 2.2.4-171-10 “Hygienic Requirements to Drinking Water Intended for Human Consumption”, it should be deepened at the expense of the control of drinking water quality in the points directly after purification (the changes to the current procedure in Ukraine were proposed) and increase of the list of the parameters. Current procedure for drinking water quality control must be expended by 9 parameters, 4 of them are “indicator ones” (including radionuclides).

2. A conceptual approach to the development of the algorithm for decision-making on the safety of drinking water in case of over-standard content of “indicator index” was developed.
3. Implementation of water quality control for the fulfillment of the requirements of the Directive 98/83/EU on drinking water needs a significant development of the control system, it includes a creation of the network of measuring laboratories, their fit with high sensitive equipment,

development of methodical support, training of personal.

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